

Formation of Musical Literacy of Primary School Students in Extracurricular Activities

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses the formation of musical literacy of primary school students in extracurricular activities. This article is an excerpt from the textbook “Music Literacy for Primary School Students” about the minutes of music literacy in primary school classes “Music Culture” and the purposeful use of interactive, interactive methods, the formation of musical impressions and the necessary knowledge, skills, abilities in music, taking into account the psychological and physiological aspects of teachers and students in the organization of music clubs, competency building, 34-hour music literacy or lessons are taught step-by-step, from simple to complex, and ways and means of achieving musical literacy through the efficient use of time are shown.

KEYWORDS: formation of musical literacy, primary school, extracurricular activities, textbook, music culture, purposeful use, interactive methods, musical impressions, necessary knowledge, skills, abilities, music, physiological aspects.

INTRODUCTION

The improvement of the education system in the country, students' perception of educational material, as well as music composition, music education, teaching methods, teaching, music UzbekLeasing remains the implementation of the facilities, extracurricular and after-school music students and other academic and theoretical work on some aspects of the scientific research has been completed and is ongoing today.

In the program “Music Culture”, in addition to teaching music to students, special attention is paid to the development of creative abilities, vocal and choral skills, musical comprehension, musical literacy, rhythmic accompaniment.

It is known that the foundation of music education in primary school is laid. It provides all the knowledge of music (singing in a choir, music literacy, listening to music, musical creativity, performing actions appropriate to music). Music literacy is not used as an independent teaching activity, but is used to perform artistic learning and performance of musical works on the basis of literacy in the process of other activities. In short, music literacy serves the educational function of the lesson.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Taking into account these educational objectives, as a result of our research, we have developed a textbook entitled “**Music Literacy for Primary School Students**” as a methodological aid during the study of musical literacy in 34-hour music culture classes. Our goal is to develop ways to achieve knowledge, skills, competencies, and competencies that are different from music literacy in music lessons, just as elementary school students learn in-depth theoretical literacy in other subjects.

The purpose of creating the textbook is to eliminate the following common mistakes in music culture lessons;

- ✓ wasting time on a simple notebook during the lesson;
- ✓ the inability of the teacher to write all the music-related symbols in the notebooks to all students during the lesson;
- ✓ deficiencies in students' writing of characters related to music;
- ✓ a state of inability to acquire sufficient theoretical knowledge in a class of one hour per week;
- ✓ cases of non-writing as written in the rules;
- ✓ cases of rapid memory loss during writing and memorization;
- inability to read given songs and melodies independently;
- cases of unsatisfactory performance of homework were identified.

Given the shortcomings and challenges, we believe that this handbook will be of great help to the younger generation, who are learning music literacy in elementary school as an additional tutorial in the classroom and in the extracurricular minute.

The textbook is divided into 6 paragraphs;

1. Introduction to teaching aids in music literacy, lines, notes, music keys, sound, location of speakers.

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2. Location of notes on the violin key.
3. The location of the notes in the bass key.
4. Signs of alteration.
5. Pause.

Dynamic characters in music.

The music lessons given in these paragraphs, along with theoretical knowledge, are presented through calligraphy methods, puzzles related to music, and various games. Various practical methods and tools of theoretical study of science are shown.

We know that it is no secret that during the lesson, the teacher organizes the lesson for students using interactive methods. But the novelty of our scientific research is that in the science of music culture the teaching of interactive methods from the five basic lines to the musical dynamic characters in the method of calligraphy is a novelty.

Consider, for example, an hour-long lesson;

Lesson 9

Topic: The division of notes, their length and the study of their elements, in this case, the students:

- ✓ will have information about the content of the first lesson, that is, what the note is, the division of the notes, their length.
- ✓ get acquainted with the name of the notes using different pictures. (Figure 1)
- ✓ learn the placement of notes on the keyboard; (Figure 2)

Figure 1

Figure2

- Learn the division of notes;

Figure 3

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- Interesting puzzles and assignments are given based on the topic; (Figures 4-5);

- Write whole, half, quarter, and half notes on a given dot with a pencil; (In this case, the student learns the notes using the method of calligraphy, their knowledge, skills, abilities are formed).

- *The whole note*

Figure 6

- *Half note*

- *Quarter note*

- ✓ *Half a quarter note*

We learn the division of notes in a poetic way! (Students' poetic memorization of the division rule of notes further increases their interest in musical literacy, influencing their psyche).

Figure 7

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- Homework; Complete this assignment independently! (allows students to complete the task independently without errors)

Figure 8

✓ *The whole note*

✓ *Half note*

✓ *Quarter note*

✓ *Half a quarter note*

- ✓ Depending on the topic, interesting puzzles and assignments are given;

Figure 9

The modern teacher has thoroughly mastered modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process, it is necessary to analyze and implement them in practice.

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Attempts have been made to eliminate the problems and shortcomings that have plagued the teacher and the student for years from the musical literacy of music culture lessons in the primary grades through the above interactive materials, calligraphy methods, and as a result;

- ✓ that there is a textbook that forms and develops literacy throughout the lesson, rather than a simple notebook;
- ✓ It is not the teacher's inability to write all the music-related notes in the notebooks for all students during the lesson, but the fact that everyone's textbook contains information about music;
- ✓ the shortcomings of students in writing musical symbols can be overcome with the help of a textbook;
- ✓ If you do not have enough theoretical knowledge in one hour a week, the textbook will help you in theoretical knowledge;
- ✓ In case of inability to write musical symbols in practice as written in the rules, the symbols related to music are eliminated by the method of calligraphy;
- ✓ in cases of rapid memorization during writing and memorization, rules, poems, and separate independent assignments were given;
- ✓ in cases of inability to read the given songs and melodies independently, students have fully mastered musical literacy;
- ✓ In case of unsatisfactory performance of homework, it was found that special attention is paid to homework in music literacy, and this textbook serves as a program for students and teachers.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the foundation of music education is formed in students studying in primary grades. Therefore, from the 1st grade onwards, the main task is to get students interested in music, to form their impressions of music, to develop the necessary musical skills and competencies.

The implementation of these tasks depends in many ways on the knowledge and skills of the teacher. At a time when the flow of information has increased dramatically, various innovations are rapidly entering our lives, independent, critical thinking skills and abilities, always ready to learn the novelty, the main goal of the educational process should be to bring up a person who is not afraid of cooperation and is able to communicate freely, and in this regard, the opening of the use of modern educational technologies in education is the right step towards achieving this goal.

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